

Analytic of MEASURABILITY AND SELECTIONS OF MULTI-FUNCTIONS IN BANACH SPACES

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Abstract

We investigate the existence of measurable selectors for multi-functions, the values of which are subsets of a Banach space that are weakly compact. We first characterize multi-functions with selectors that are robustly measurable. Regarding the nonethless, we demonstrate that each multi-function that is scalarly measurable admits Selectors with scalar measurable values. No presumptions about separability are necessary for the spaces of ranges.

Introduction

We study properties of strong measurability of ω^* -densities of vector measures and operators.

The following concepts are needed here: the function $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ are said to be ω^* -scalarly measurable (resp. μ -Gelfand integrable) if for every $x^2 \in E$ the functions $\langle x^2, \psi_j \rangle: \Omega_j \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by $t \mapsto \langle x^2, \psi_j(t) \rangle$ is measurable (resp. μ -integrable). If ψ_j is Gelfand integrable, then for each $A_j \in \Sigma$ there exists a vector $\int_{A_j} \sum_j \psi_j d\mu \in E^*$ (called the Gelfand integral of ψ_j over A_j) satisfying

$$\langle x^2, \int_{A_j} \sum_j \psi_j d\mu \rangle = \int_{A_j} \sum_j \langle x^2, \psi_j \rangle d\mu \text{ for every } x^2 \in E.$$

For basic information about the Gelfand integral see [5, p. 53-54].

With the help of the lifting theorem (see below) it can be proved that given a μ -continuous (norm) vector measure of bounded variation $m: \Sigma \rightarrow E^*$ there exists a Gelfand integrable functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ satisfying

$$(I) \langle x^2, \sum_j m(A_j) \rangle = \sum_j \int_{A_j} \langle x^2, \psi_j(t) \rangle d\mu,$$

for every $x^2 \in E$ and $A_j \in \Sigma$, see [17, theorem 11.1, p. 236]. If we think in terms of continuous linear operators $T: L^1(\mu) \rightarrow E^*$, the application of the previous result to the vector measure $m(A_j) = T(\chi_{A_j})$ provides a ω^* -measurable functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ with the property

$$(I') \langle x^2, \sum_j T(f_j) \rangle = \int_{\Omega_j} \sum_j \langle x^2, \psi_j(t) \rangle f_j(t) d\mu,$$

for every $x^2 \in E$ and for every $f_j \in L^1(\mu)$. It is pointed out in [5, p. 84], that the existence of such a ω^* -measurable functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ satisfying (I') is "mostly an esthetic generalization of the representation results that deal with Bochner integrability, because the measurability properties of the kernel ψ_j are not, in general, strong enough to exhibit structural properties of the operator under representation". In terms of vector measures the following example, [17, Example 3.1, p.186], illustrate the comment above.

Example 1.1. Let μ be the Lebesgue measure on $[0; 1]$, Σ the Lebesgue measurable sets and $m: \Sigma \rightarrow \ell_2([0,1])$ the null vector measure i.e. $\sum_j m(A_j) = 0$ for every $A_j \in \Sigma$. Clearly the null function is a (strongly measurable) Gelfand derivative (in fact the Radon-Nikodým derivative of m). On the other hand, let $\{e_t: t \in [0,1]\}$ be the canonical base of the Hilbert space $\ell_2([0,1])$. The functions $f_j: [0,1] \rightarrow \ell_2([0,1])$ defined by $f_j(t) = e_t, t \in [0,1]$ satisfies that $\langle x^2, f_j(t) \rangle = 0, \mu$ -almost everywhere, for every $x^2 \in \ell_2([0,1])$. So f_j is ω^* -measurable and satisfies (I) but it is not strongly measurable.

We show that for vector measures m as those considered here the ω^* -measurable functions ψ_j verifying (I) can be obtained with an additional property that avoids the commented pathologies.

In what follows we fix a lifting $\rho: \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma$ on (Ω_j, Σ, μ) , see [13, p. 46, Theorem 3], [9, 341K] and [21, Appendix G]. Recall that ρ satisfies the following properties:

- (1) If $A_j, B_j \in \Sigma$ and $\mu(A_j \Delta B_j) = 0$ then $\rho(A_j) = \rho(B_j)$;
- (2) $\sum_j \mu(\rho(A_j) \Delta A_j) = 0$ for every $A_j \in \Sigma$;
- (3) $\rho(A_j \cap B_j) = \rho(A_j) \cap \rho(B_j)$ for every $A_j, B_j \in \Sigma$;
- (4) $\rho(\emptyset) = \emptyset, \rho(\Omega_j) = \Omega_j$;
- (5) $\rho(\Omega_j \setminus A_j) = \Omega_j \setminus \rho(A_j)$ for every $A_j \in \Sigma$;
- (6) $\rho(A_j \cup B_j) = \rho(A_j) \cup \rho(B_j)$ for every $A_j, B_j \in \Sigma$.

We note that the lifting ρ can be extended to a map $\rho: L^\infty(\mu) \rightarrow L^\infty(\mu)$ that assigns to each equivalence class $f_j \in L^\infty(\mu)$ a function $\rho(f_j) \in f_j$.

The following lemma is needed later [24]. The definition of Γ_{B_j} below is given in equation (1).

Lemma 1.2. If $B_j \in \Sigma^+$, $\Gamma_{B_j} = \Gamma_{\rho(B_j)}$.

Proof. Observe that for any $B'_j \in \Sigma_{B_j}^+$ we have that $\rho(B'_j) \subseteq \rho(B_j), \mu(\rho(B'_j)) = \mu(B'_j)$ and $m(\rho(B'_j)) = m(B'_j)$ by μ -continuity. Therefore

$$\sum_j \frac{m(B'_j)}{\mu(B'_j)} = \sum_j \frac{m(\rho(B'_j))}{\mu(\rho(B'_j))} \in \Gamma_{\rho(B_j)}$$

which means that $\Gamma_{B_j} \subseteq \Gamma_{\rho(B_j)}$.

Conversely, if $B'_j \subseteq \rho(B_j)$ then $B'_j = B'_j \cap (B_j \cup (\rho(B_j) \setminus B_j))$ and $\sum_j \mu(\rho(B_j) \setminus B_j) = 0$ implies that $\sum_j \mu(B'_j \cap B_j) = \sum_j \mu(B'_j)$ and $\sum_j m(B'_j \cap B_j) = \sum_j m(B'_j)$. Consequently

$$\sum_j \frac{m(B'_j)}{\mu(B'_j)} = \sum_j \frac{m(B'_j \cap B_j)}{\mu(B'_j \cap B_j)} \in \sum_j \Gamma_{B_j},$$

and the proof is over.

Proposition 1.3. If $m: \Sigma \rightarrow E^*$ is a μ -continuous (norm) vector measure of bounded variation, then there is a ω^* -measurable functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ with the following properties:

(I) $\langle x^2, \sum_j m(A_j) \rangle = \int_{A_j} \sum_j \langle x^2, \psi_j(t) \rangle d\mu$ for every $x^2 \in E$ and $A_j \in \Sigma$;

(II) if $A_j \in \Sigma$, then $\psi_j(t) \in \overline{\Gamma_{A_j}}^{\omega^*}$ for μ -almost every $t \in A_j$.

Proof. The existence of a ω^* -measurable functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ verifying condition (I) is proved by Musial in [17, theorem 11.1, p. 236]. Here we refine his construction to obtain a function that also satisfies the second condition.

We assume first that there exists $M > 0$ such that $\sum_j \|m(A_j)\| \leq M \sum_j \mu(A_j)$ for each $A_j \in \Sigma$. Following Musial's proof, for every $x^2 \in (B_j)_E$ we consider a μ -Radon- Nikodým derivative $(g_j)_{x^2} \in L^\infty(\mu)$ of the scalar measure $\langle x^2, m \rangle$. The functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ given by $\sum_j \psi_j(t)(x^2) = \sum_j \rho((g_j)_{x^2})(t)$ is well-defined, ω^* -measurable and satisfies (I).

We show now that ψ_j also verifies (II). For every finite partition π of Ω_j into Σ -sets we write

$$s_\pi := \sum_{A_j \in \pi} \sum_j \frac{m(A_j)}{\mu(A_j)} \chi_{A_j}$$

Fix $x^2 \in (B_j)_E$. By [5, lemma 1, p. 67] the net

$$\langle x^2, s_\pi \rangle = \sum_{A_j \in \pi} \sum_j \frac{\langle x^2, m \rangle(A_j)}{\mu(A_j)} \chi_{A_j}$$

converges in $L^\infty(\mu)$ to $(g_j)_{x^2}$ when considering partitions ordered by refinement and with the agreement that $0/0 = 0$. Hence

$$\rho(\langle x^2, s_\pi \rangle) = \sum_{A_j \in \pi} \sum_j \frac{\langle x^2, m \rangle(A_j)}{\mu(A_j)} \chi_{\rho(A_j)}$$

converges to $\rho((g_j)_{x^2})$ uniformly in Ω_j because of the continuity property of ρ , see [13,p. 35].

With all the above, if we define

$$\rho(s_\pi) = \sum_{A_j \in \pi} \sum_j \frac{m(A_j)}{\mu(A_j)} \chi_{\rho(A_j)},$$

then the net $\rho(s_\pi)(t) \omega^*$ -converges to $\psi_j(t)$ for every $t \in \Omega_j$. For the given A_j , if $t \in A_j \cap \rho(A_j)$ then $\psi_j(t)$ is also the ω^* -limit of $\rho(s_\pi)(t)$ when taking only partitions π finer than $\{\rho(A_j), \Omega_j \setminus \rho(A_j)\}$, so $\psi_j(t) \in \overline{\Gamma_{\rho(A_j)}}^{\omega^*}$. Bearing in mind now Lemma 3.2 we conclude that $\psi_j(t) \in \overline{\Gamma_{A_j}}^{\omega^*}$ for μ -almost every $t \in A_j$, and the validity of condition (II) is stated.

Now we deal with the general case. Fix a partition $\{(\Omega_j)_n: n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ of Ω_j , such that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists $M_n > 0$ verifying

$$\left\| \sum_j m(A_j \cap (\Omega_j)_n) \right\| \leq M_n \sum_j \mu(A_j \cap (\Omega_j)_n).$$

for each $A_j \in \Sigma$, see [5, p. 63, Theorem 5]. Defining $(A_j)_n := \rho((\Omega_j)_n)$, we obtain a sequence $(A_j)_n \in \mathbb{N}$ of pairwise disjoint sets with $\sum_j \mu(\Omega_j \setminus \cup_n (A_j)_n) = 0$ and satisfying

$$\left\| \sum_j m(A_j \cap (A_j)_n) \right\| \leq M_n \sum_j \mu(A_j \cap (A_j)_n).$$

for every $A_j \in \Sigma$. Note that the restriction of ρ to $\sum_{(A_j)_n}$ is a lifting on $((A_j)_n, \sum_j (A_j)_n, \mu)$ so we can apply the first part in order to deduce the existence of ω^* -measurable function $(\psi_j)_n: (A_j)_n \rightarrow E^*$ satisfying the conditions (I) and (II). It is clear that $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ defined as $\sum_j \psi_j = \sum_{n=1}^\infty \sum_j (\psi_j)_n \chi_{(A_j)_n}$ is ω^* -measurable. If $x^2 \in E$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\cup_{i=1}^n A_n} \sum_j |\langle x^2, \psi_j \rangle| d\mu &= \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_j \int_{(A_j)_i} |\langle x^2, \psi_j \rangle| d\mu = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_j |\langle x^2, m \rangle|((A_j)_i) \\ &\leq \sum_j \|x^2\| |m|(\Omega_j) < \infty \end{aligned}$$

so $|\langle x^2, \psi_j \rangle| \in L^1(\mu)$ by the monotone convergence theorem. Moreover, the dominated convergence theorem implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j \langle x^2, m(A_j) \rangle &= \sum_{n=1}^\infty \langle x^2, \sum_j m(A_j \cap (A_j)_n) \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^\infty \int \sum_j |\langle x^2, (\psi_j)_n \rangle| d\mu \\ &= \int \sum_j |\langle x^2, \psi_j \rangle| d\mu \end{aligned}$$

for every $A_j \in \Sigma$.

The function ψ_j also satisfies (II). Indeed, if $A_j \in \Sigma$ then for μ -almost every $t \in \cup_n (A_j \cap (A_j)_n)$ the element $\psi_j(t) \in \cup_n \overline{\Gamma_{A_j \cap (A_j)_n}}^{\omega^*} \subseteq \overline{\Gamma_{A_j}}^{\omega^*}$

Definition 1.4. If $m: \Sigma \rightarrow E^*$ is a μ -continuous (norm) vector measure of bounded variation, we say that a ω^* -measurable functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ is a Gelfand derivative of m if it satisfies (I) and (II) of Proposition 3.3.

If $f_j, g_j \in (E^*)^{\Omega_j}$ the distance between f_j and g_j is

$$d(f_j, g_j) := \sup\{\|f_j(t) - g_j(t)\| : t \in \Omega_j\} \in [0, +\infty]$$

For $F \subseteq E^*$ we write $\mathcal{M}(\mu, F, E^*)$ (resp. $\mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, E^*)$) to denote the subset of all functions in $(E^*)^{\Omega_j}$ which are strongly measurable (resp. Bochner integrable) and μ -essentially F -valued.

Proposition 1.5. Let $m: \Sigma \rightarrow F$ be a μ -continuous measure of bounded variation with values in a Banach space F . If E^* is a dual Banach space which contains isometrically $F (i: F \rightarrow E^*)$ then every Gelfand derivative $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ of m verifies that

$$\mathcal{R}(m) = d(\psi_j, \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, E^*)) = d(\psi_j, \mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, E^*))$$

In particular, if $\mathcal{R}(m) = 0$ then ψ_j is a Radon-Nikodým derivative of m .

Proof. The proof is similar to the one of [2, Theorem 2.3]. We identify the elements of F with their image in E^* so that we can write $\Gamma_{B_j} = \Gamma_{B_j}^{\mu,m} = \Gamma_{B_j}^{\mu,iom}$.

Suppose that $d(\psi_j, \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, E^*)) < \varepsilon$ so we can find $g_j \in \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, E^*)$ satisfying $\sum_j \|\psi_j(t) - g_j(t)\| < \varepsilon$ for every $t \in \Omega_j$. If $(s_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence of simple F -valued functions that converges μ -a. e. to g_j then, by Egorov's theorem [6, p. 94, Theorem 1], there exists a set D verifying $\mu(\Omega_j \setminus D) < \mu(A_j)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\sum_j \|\psi_j(t) - (s_n^j)(t)\| < \varepsilon$ for every $t \in D$. Clearly $A_j \cap D \in \Sigma^+$, and using that (s_n^j) is simple there are $(x^2 - \epsilon) \in F$ and $B_j \in \Sigma_{A_j \cap D}^+$ with $\sum_j \|\psi_j(t) - (x^2 - \epsilon)\| < \varepsilon$ for all $t \in B_j$. Hence, if $B'_j \in \Sigma_{B_j}^+$ and $x^2 \in (B_j)_E$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j |\langle x^2, m(B'_j) \rangle - \mu(B'_j) \langle x^2, (x^2 - \epsilon) \rangle| &= \sum_j \left| \int_{B'_j} \langle x^2, \psi_j \rangle d\mu - \int_{B'_j} \langle x^2, (x^2 - \epsilon) \rangle d\mu \right| \\ &\leq \varepsilon \sum_j \mu(B'_j) \end{aligned}$$

Taking the supremum on $x^2 \in (B_j)_E$ we deduce $\sum_j \|m(B'_j) - \mu(B'_j)(x^2 - \epsilon)\| \leq \varepsilon \sum_j \mu(B'_j)$. Therefore $\Gamma_{B_j} \subseteq B_j((x^2 - \epsilon), \varepsilon)$ and $\text{rad}(\Gamma_{B_j}) < \varepsilon$. This shows that $\mathcal{R}(m) \leq d(\psi_j, \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, \Sigma^+))$.

Fix $\varepsilon > \mathcal{R}(m)$. Given $A_j \in \Sigma^+$ there exists $\tilde{B}_j \in \Sigma_{A_j}^+$ and $(x^2 - \epsilon) \in F$ such that $\overline{\Gamma_{\tilde{B}_j}}^{\omega^*}$ is contained in the ball $(B_j)_{E^*}((x^2 - \epsilon), \varepsilon)$. If B_j is the set of all $t \in \tilde{B}_j$ verifying that $\psi_j(t)$ belongs to this ball, then $B_j \in \Sigma_{\tilde{B}_j}^+$ by property (II) and the fact that μ is complete. In other words, for every $A_j \in \Sigma^+$ there exists $B_j \in \Sigma_{A_j}^+$ and $(x^2 - \epsilon) \in E^*$ with $\|\psi_j(t) - (x^2 - \epsilon)\| < \varepsilon$ for each $t \in B_j$. By an exhaustion argument we can construct a countable family of disjoint sets $(B_j)_n: n \in \mathbb{N}$ with $\mu(\Omega_j \setminus \cup_n (B_j)_n) = 0$ and a sequence of elements $((x^2 - \epsilon)_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in F with the previous property so that $\sum_j g_j = \sum_j \sum_n (x^2 - \epsilon)_n \chi_{(B_j)_n} + \sum_j f_j \chi_{\Omega_j \setminus \cup (B_j)_n}$ is an integrable function satisfying $\sum_j \|\psi_j(t) - g_j(t)\| < \varepsilon$ for every $t \in B_j$. The fact that g_j is integrable is consequence of the monotone convergence theorem since

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\cup_{i=1}^m (B_j)_n} \sum_j \|g_j\| d\mu &= \sum_{n=1}^m \sum_j \|(x^2 - \epsilon)_n\| \mu((B_j)_n) \leq \sum_{n=1}^m \sum_j \left(\varepsilon + \frac{\|m((B_j)_n)\|}{\mu((B_j)_n)} \right) \mu((B_j)_n) \\ &\leq \varepsilon + \sum_j |m|(\Omega_j) \end{aligned}$$

for every $m \in \mathbb{N}$. This shows that $d(\psi_j, \mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, E^*)) \leq \mathcal{R}(m)$.

On the other hand, the inequality $\sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, E^*)) \leq \sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, E^*))$ is obvious.

Observe that the proof shows that $\mathcal{R}(m)$ is finite if and only if any of the distances $\sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, E^*))$ or $\sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, E^*))$ is finite, so the equality remains true if one of these indexes is infinity. Finally, if $\mathcal{R}(m) = 0$ then $\sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, E^*)) = 0$ so ψ_j is a Bochner integrable function with values in F almost everywhere that satisfies

$$\sum_j \langle x^2, m(A_j) \rangle = \int_{A_j} \sum_j \langle x^2, \psi_j(t) \rangle d\mu = \sum_j \langle x^2, \int_{A_j} \psi_j d\mu \rangle \text{ for every } x^2 \in E \text{ and } A_j \in \Sigma,$$

Therefore

$$\sum_j m(A_j) = \int_{A_j} \sum_j \psi_j d\mu \text{ for every } A_j \in \Sigma,$$

Remark 1.6.

(i) Notice that although a Gelfand derivative $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ may take values out of F we can control $\sum$ for μ -almost every $t \in \Omega_j$.

(ii) If we replace in (II) the condition

$$\sum_j \psi_j(t) \in \overline{\Gamma_{A_j}}^{\omega^*}$$

by the condition (II')

$$\sum_j \psi_j(t) \in \overline{\text{co}}^{\omega^*} \Gamma_{A_j},$$

then Proposition 3.5 is also valid.

Immediate consequences of the previous Propositions are the following corollaries (see [24]).

Corollary 1.7. Let $m: \Sigma \rightarrow F$ be a μ -continuous measure of bounded variation with values in a Banach space F . If $i: F \hookrightarrow F^{**}$ is the canonical inclusion in the bidual then every Gelfand derivative $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow F^{**}$ verifies that

$$\mathcal{R}(m) = \sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, F^{**})) = \sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, F^{**}))$$

In particular, if $\mathcal{R}(m) = 0$ then ψ_j is a Radon-Nikodým derivative of m .

Corollary 1.8. Let $T: L^1(\mu) \rightarrow F$ be a continuous linear operator. For every dual Banach space E^* containing F isometrically ($i: F \hookrightarrow F^{**}$) there is a ω^* -measurable sequence of functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ with the following properties:

(A) $\sum \langle x^2, i \circ T(f_j) \rangle = \int_{\Omega_j} \sum_j \langle x^2, \psi_j(t) \rangle f_j(t) d\mu$ for every $x^2 \in E$ and $f_j \in L^1(\mu)$;

(B) if $A_j \in \Sigma$ then $\sum_j \psi_j(t) \in \sum_j \overline{\left\{ \frac{i \circ T(\chi_{B_j})}{\mu(B_j)} : B_j \in \Sigma_{A_j}^+ \right\}}^{\omega^*}$ for μ -almost every $t \in A_j$.

For every sequence of functions $\psi_j: \Omega_j \rightarrow E^*$ satisfying (A) and (B) we have that

$$d(T, L_{rep}(L^1(\mu), F)) = \sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{M}(\mu, F, E^*)) = \sum_j d(\psi_j, \mathcal{L}^1(\mu, F, F^*)) \in [0, \infty]$$

In addition, if T is representable then the sequence ψ_j is a density of T .

Proof. Combine Propositions 2.7 and 3.5.

Example 1.9. Let $([0,1], \mathcal{M}, \lambda)$ be the Lebesgue measure and $m: \mathcal{M} \rightarrow L^1(\lambda)$ the vector measure given by $m(A_j) = \chi_{A_j}$. For every lifting ρ on the previous probability space, the sequence of functions $\psi_j: [0,1] \rightarrow L^1(\lambda)^{**}$ that associates to each $t \in \Omega_j$ the finitely additive measure $\nu_t: \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined as

$$\nu_t(A_j) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \notin \rho(A_j) \\ 1 & \text{if } t \in \rho(A_j) \end{cases}$$

is a Gelfand derivative of m . Moreover $\mathcal{R}(m) = 1$ and $d(\psi_j(t), L^1(\lambda)) = 1$ for λ -almost every $t \in [0,1]$.

Proof. We consider $L^1(\lambda)$ as a subspace of $L^1(\lambda)^{**}$ which consists of all finitely additive λ -continuous (scalar) measures on $\mathcal{M}$ endowed with the norm $|\nu|(\Omega_j)$ (total variation). The

space $L^1(\lambda)$ is identified with its countably additive elements (see [23, theorem 2.3, p. 53]). The functions ψ_j is well-defined and verifies for every $A_j, B_j \in \Sigma$

$$\int_{A_j} \sum_j \langle \chi_{B_j}, \nu_t \rangle d\lambda = \sum_j \int_{A_j} \int_{[0,1]} \chi_{B_j} d\nu_t d\lambda = \int_{A_j} \sum_j \chi_{\rho(B_j)}(t) d\lambda = \sum_j \langle \chi_{B_j}, m(A_j) \rangle.$$

Extending this expression by linearity for simple functions and by density to all the elements of $L^\infty(\lambda)$ we deduce that ψ_j verifies (I).

We have now to check (II). Given $A_j \in \mathcal{M}$ we will see that $\psi_j(s^2) \in \overline{\Gamma_{A_j}}^{\omega^*}$ for every $s^2 \in A_j \cap \rho(A_j)$. Fix a ω^* -open neighbourhood of $\psi_j(s^2)$ of the form

$$W = \{((x^{**})^2 - \epsilon) \in L^1(\lambda)^{**} : \sum_j | \langle (x^{**})^2 - \psi_j(s^2), (h_j)_i \rangle | < \epsilon \text{ for every } i = 1, \dots, m\}$$

where $(h_j)_i \in L^\infty(\lambda)$. We are going to show that it intersects Γ_{A_j} . Since simple functions are dense in $L^\infty(\lambda)$, we can assume that each function $(h_j)_i$ can be written as $\sum_j (h_j)_i = \sum_{i=1}^{k_i} \sum_j a_j^i \chi_{\rho((A_j)_j^i)}$ where the family $\{\rho((A_j)_j^i) : j = 1, \dots, k_i\}$ is a finite partition of Ω_j for every $i = 1, \dots, m$. Denoting by C_j the intersection of $\rho(A_j) \cap A_j$ with the sets $\rho((A_j)_j^i)$ containing s among its elements, we deduce that $C_j \in \mathcal{M}_{A_j}^+$. Moreover for every i we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j \left| \left\langle \frac{\chi_{C_j}}{\mu(C_j)} - \psi_j(s^2), (h_j)_i \right\rangle \right| &= \sum_j \left| \sum_{j=1}^{k_i} a_j^i \left(\frac{\mu(C_j \cap \rho((A_j)_j^i))}{\mu(C_j)} - \nu_{s^2}(\rho((A_j)_j^i)) \right) \right| \\ &= \left| \sum_{j=1}^{k_i} a_j^i 0 \right| = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore ψ_j is a Gelfand derivative of m .

We know that $\mathcal{R}(m) = 1$ by Example 2.5, but we also have that $\sum_j d(\psi_j(t), L^1(\mu)) = 1$ for almost every $t \in [0,1]$. To see this last assertion note that for almost every $t \in [0,1]$ we can find a decreasing sequence of sets $(A_j)_n = \rho((A_j)_n)$ containing t and with $\lim_n \lambda((A_j)_n) = 1$.

Therefore, given a λ -continuous countably additive measure $(1 + \epsilon) : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ we have that

$$\| \nu_t - (1 + \epsilon) \| \geq \sum_j |1 - (1 + \epsilon)(A_j)_n| \text{ for every } n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Using that $\lim_n \sum_j (1 + \epsilon)(A_j)_n = 0$ we conclude the result.

Example 1.10. Let $([0,1], \mathcal{M}, \lambda)$ be as above and consider the vector measure $m : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow c_0$ from Example 2.6 given by

$$\sum_j m(A_j) = \sum_j \left(\int_{A_j} r_n^j(t)(t) d\lambda \right)_n$$

The function $\psi_j : [0,1] \rightarrow \ell^\infty$ defined as $\psi_j(t) = (r_n^j(t))_n$ is a Gelfand derivative of m .

Moreover $\mathcal{R}(m) = 1$ and $\sum_j d(\psi_j(t), c_0) = 1$ for λ -almost every $t \in [0,1]$.

Proof. Fix an arbitrary $A_j \in \Sigma^+$. For every $x_n^2(t)_n \in \ell^1 = c_0^*$ we have that

$$\sum_j \int_{A_j} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_n^2 r_n^j(t)(t) d\lambda = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_j \int_{A_j} r_n^j(t) x_n^2(t) d\lambda$$

by the dominated convergence theorem, which shows (I).

To see (II) take the subset A'_j of A_j which consists of all elements of A_j that remain when removing those $t \in A_j$ which are dyadic numbers, (i.e. those of the form $t = k/2^n$ for some $k, n \in \mathbb{N}$) as well as those which belong to a μ -null set of the form

$$\{t \in A_j: (r_n^j(t))_{n=1}^m = (a_n)_{n=1}^m\}$$

for some $(a_n)_{n=1}^m \in \{-1, 1\}^m$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Note that we have removed a countable number of μ -null sets, so $A'_j \subseteq A_j$ verifies $\sum_j \mu(A_j) = \sum_j \mu(A'_j)$.

We are going to prove that $(r_n^j(t)(s^2))_n \in \overline{\Gamma_{A_j}}^{\omega^*}$ for each $s^2 \in A'_j$, which will show (II). In order to simplify the notation we will prove that a ω^* -open neighbourhood of $(r_n^j(t)(s^2))_n$ of the form

$$V = \left\{ (x_n^2 - \epsilon)_n \in \ell^\infty: \left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_n^2 \left((x_n^2 - \epsilon)_n - r_n^j(t)(s^2) \right) \right| < \epsilon \right\} \text{ (for some } (x_n^2)_n \in \ell^1)$$

intersects Γ_{A_j} . The general case of an arbitrary ω^* -neighbourhood is analogous.

We start by fixing $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\sum_{n>m_0} |x_n^2| < \epsilon/2$. If $s^2 \in A'_j$ then $B_j := \{t \in A'_j: (r_n^j(t))_{n=1}^{m_0} = (r_n^j(s^2))_{n=1}^{m_0}\}$ is an element of Σ with positive measure (because of the construction of A'_j), so

$$\sum_j \frac{\int_{B_j} r_n^j(t) d\mu}{\mu(B_j)} = \sum_j \frac{r_n^j(s^2) \mu(B_j)}{\mu(B_j)} = \sum_j r_n^j(s^2) \text{ for } n = 1, \dots, m_0.$$

Therefore $m(B_j)/\mu(B_j) \in V$ since

$$\left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_n^2 \sum_j \left(\frac{\int_{B_j} r_n^j(t) d\mu}{\mu(B_j)} - r_n^j(s^2) \right) \right| \leq 2 \sum_{n>m_0} |x_n^2| < \epsilon.$$

We know that $\mathcal{R}(m) = 1$ by Example 2.6. Finally, note that the sequence $\psi_j(t)$ has range in $\{-1, 1\}^{\mathbb{N}}$ for every t which is not dyadic, so $\sum_j d(\psi_j(t), c_0) = 1$ for λ -almost everywhere.

Conclusions

The study explores measurable selectors for weakly compact Banach spaces, demonstrating that scalarly measurable multi-functions admit scalar measurable selectors, without requiring separability assumptions for range spaces.

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